

PHYTOCHEMICAL AND ANTIBACTERIAL ANALYSES OF GINGER (*ZINGIBER OFFICINALE*) AND GARLIC (*ALLIUM SATIVUM*) EXTRACTS ON SOME CLINICAL ISOLATES

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ABSTRACT

Garlic (*allium Sativum L.*) and Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*), were chosen to examine their effects on selected bacterial isolates. In the present study, their extracts were made using distilled water and ethanol as extractive solvent and the extracts were tested for their antibacterial effect against *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. The antibacterial effects of various garlic and ginger extracts were evaluated using various standard methods. The extracted aqueous and ethanol extracts were applied to the bacterial isolates through the agar diffusion method. The diameter for zone of inhibition for aqueous extract of garlic ranged from 10.10±0.01 to 25.10±0.03 mm for the various concentrations used. The diameter for zone of inhibition for ethanol extract of garlic ranged from 11.00±0.01 to 28.11±0.01 mm for the various concentrations. Maximum inhibitory effect for aqueous extract of garlic was towards *Klebsiella pneumonia*, while that of ethanol was towards *Staphylococcus aureus*. The diameter of zone of inhibition for aqueous extract of ginger ranged from 5.00±0.01 to 18.01±0.03 mm for the various concentrations used. The diameter of zone of inhibition for ethanol extract of ginger ranged from 5.03±0.01 to 24.01±0.20 mm for the various concentrations used. Maximum inhibitory effect for aqueous extract of ginger was towards *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, while that of ethanol was towards *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The results of this present study has shown that test bacteria were susceptible to crude extracts of garlic and ginger *in vitro* which means the plants extracts possess antibacterial properties. It is recommended that further research can be done towards isolating, purifying and standardizing the active antibacterial ingredients in both plant materials.

Keywords: Antimicrobial, Extract, Garlic, Ginger, Phytochemical

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants play a significant role in providing primary health care services to rural people and are used by about 80 % of the marginal communities around the world (Latif *et al.*, 2003; Shinwari *et al.*, 2006). Each medicinal plant species has its own nutrient composition besides having pharmacologically important phytochemicals. These nutrients are essential for the physiological functions of the human body. Such nutrients and biochemicals like carbohydrates, fats and proteins play an important role in satisfying human needs for energy and life processes (Dingman, 2002). These medicinal plants are used by marginal

communities to cure various diseases. As various medicinal plant species are used either in the form of extract or decoction by the local people in different regions, therefore, evaluating their nutritional significance can help to understand the worth of these plants species in different ecological conditions. Garlic (*Allium sativum*) in the family Liliaceae is a perennial bulb-forming plant. Garlic is naturally a good source of therapeutic agents. Garlic is an ethno pharmaceutical drug but also proved to have therapeutic effects by different scientific studies allicin an organosulfur compound, which prevents lipids from biosynthesis (Ashfaq *et al.*, 2021). Louis Pasteur was the first to describe the antibacterial effect of garlic juices (Penecilla and Magno, 2011). Garlic has been found to exhibit antibacterial activity against a wide range of Gram negative and Gram-positive bacteria, including multidrug-resistant strains (Pundir and Jain, 2010; Bakht *et al.*, 2011; Gull *et al.*, 2012). Garlic is a very important natural plant that is used as an alternative medicine for management of typhoid fever and it can be used alongside conventional antibiotics to fight agents of nosocomial infections that are now prevalent in hospitals (Abubakar, 2009). The most important chemical compounds of garlic which was thought to be responsible for antimicrobial activity are the organosulphur compound including allicin (Hovana *et al.*, 2011). It showed better antibacterial activity than streptomycin and ampicillin (Ilić *et al.*, 2012). Allicin exhibits its antimicrobial activity mainly by immediate and total inhibition of ribonucleic acid (RNA) synthesis, although deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) and protein syntheses are also partially inhibited, suggesting that RNA is the primary target of allicin action (Durairaj *et al.*, 2009). Moreover, garlic is known to inhibit cell wall synthesis because it inhibits trans-peptidation enzymes involved in the cross-linking of the polysaccharide chains of the bacterial cell wall and also activates lytic enzymes (Eja *et al.*, 2007). Joe *et al.* (2009) postulated that the antibacterial and antifungal properties of garlic juice are due to the inhibition of succinic dehydrogenase via the inactivation of thiol group. The ability of garlic to inhibit the growth of both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria shows that it has a broad spectrum of activity and can be used for formulation and development of newer broad spectrum antibacterial substances and it provides scientific basis for its utilization in traditional and folk medicine (Meriga *et al.*, 2012; Penecilla and

Magno, 2011). The research of Victor and Igeleke (2012) found that garlic has very strong antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Salmonella typhi*. Joe *et al.* (2009) evaluated the antimicrobial activity of garlic extract against *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Morganella morgani*, *Candida albicans*, *Escherichia coli* and *Proteus vulgaris*. Ginger (*Z. officinale*) is used as delicacy or medicine (Malu *et al.*, 2009). *Zingiber* is native to tropical Southeast Asia and cultivated in the West Indies, Africa and India. A mixture of zingerone, shogaols and gingerols causes the characteristic odour and flavour of ginger root (White, 2007). Ginger compounds are active against diarrhoea and treatment of nausea caused by sea sickness, morning sickness and chemotherapy (Langner *et al.*, 1998; Chan *et al.*, 2009). Studies conducted show that crude extracts of ginger in combination with lime inhibited *Staphylococcus* spp. (Riazur *et al.*, 2011).

The aim was to evaluate the phytochemical and antibacterial properties of Garlic (*Allium Sativum L.*) and Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) extract on some clinical isolates.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and Identification of Plant material

Ginger and garlic were bought from Oba market and Uselu market in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. The plants were identified by Dr. Akinibosun from the Department of Plant Biology and Biotechnology, University of Benin, Edo State. The rhizomes of both plants were washed thoroughly of soil particles, they were then peeled, washed, sliced and air dried in the laboratory. The dried material of garlic and ginger were grinded to powder. Fifty grammes (50 g) of powdered ginger and garlic were weighed into separate big bottles containing 500 ml of distilled water and 500 ml of ethanol. The solution was left for three days to soak. Each of the solution was filtered with Whatman No. 1 filter paper. The filtrates were collected and concentrated in a water bath at 40°C to get the crude extract from which different concentrations were prepared. The prepared extract from aqueous solution and ethanol solution were stored in the freezer until needed.

Preparation of different concentrations from aqueous and ethanolic extract

A concentration of 100 mg/ml of the both extracts was prepared by dissolving 1g of the extract in 10 ml of sterile distilled water. Then concentrations of 50 mg/ml, 25 mg/ml, 12.5 mg/ml were prepared from the stock concentration (100 mg/ml) by double dilution method (Ekwenye and Elegalam, 2005).

Determination of phytochemical constituents of Ginger and garlic

The phytochemical screening was carried out on ginger and garlic to determine the presence of the alkaloid, saponin, steroids, flavonoid, tannin and cardiac glycoside using the method of Edeoga *et al.* (2005).

Source of microbes

The microbes were collected from the Medical Laboratory of the University of Benin Teaching Hospital. The bacteria were sub-cultured aseptically onto nutrient agar. Bacteria collected include: *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Escherichia coli* and *Streptococcus pneumonia*. The identity of the bacteria isolates were confirmed using standard biochemical and physiological tests as described by (Cheesebrough, 2000).

Standardization of Inoculum

The method of Chapin and Lauderdale (2003) was used in standardizing the inoculums. The inoculums were standardized according to Macfarlan standard at a wavelength of 600 nm.

Antibacterial analysis

Antibacterial activity was carried out by the method of Eloff (1998) by noting the zone of inhibition against the test organisms. Twenty four hour (24 h) old culture of each of the test isolates were transferred aseptically into 10 ml sterile normal saline in a test tube and mixed thoroughly for even distribution. A sterile cotton swab was then used to uniformly spread the suspension on the oven dried disposable plates with nutrient agar. Three (3) adequately spaced wells of diameter 4 mm per plate were made on the

culture media surface respectively using a sterile metal cup-borer. 0.2 ml of each extract and control were put in each hole under aseptic condition. The plates were left standing on the laboratory bench for at least one hour for diffusion before transferring them into the incubator. Conventional antibiotics were used as positive controls for bacteria and distilled water was used as negative control. All the plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 h. the zones of inhibition were measured and recorded after incubation. Zones of inhibition around the wells indicated antimicrobial activity of the extracts against the test organisms. The diameter of these zones were measured diagonally in millimeter with ruler and then mean values for each organism from the triplicate culture was recorded.

Determination of minimum inhibitory concentration

The nutrient agar was prepared and poured into sterile disposable petridishes and allowed to solidify. The media was inoculated with the test isolates. The discs soaked in different concentrations of the extract were placed on the surface of the seeded nutrient agar plates. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours and then examined for growth. The MIC was taken as the lowest concentration that prevented the growth of the test bacteria.

Minimum bacteriocidal concentration (MBC)

A loopful of the content of each plate in the MIC determination above, which did not show any visible growth after the period of incubation was streaked unto freshly prepared nutrient agar. This was carried out to determine their MBC and then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours after which it was observed for visible growth. The lowest concentration of the subculture with no growth was considered as minimum bacteriocidal concentration.

Antibiotic sensitivity disc

Ciprofloxacin a broad spectrum antibiotics was used in this study. Sterile water was used as negative control.

Proximate analysis

The method described in AOAC, (2002) were used to analyze the proximate composition of ginger and garlic for the protein, fat, fibre, ash and moisture, while carbohydrate was calculated by subtracting the sum of the values of the other nutrients from 100.

Statistical analysis

The experiment was set up in triplicate and the results represent mean± SEM.

RESULTS

Table 1 result shows that alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, steroids, tannin and cardiac glycoside were present in both garlic and ginger extracts, while steroids was absent from the aqueous extract of both garlic and ginger. Table 2 represent the proximate composition of garlic and ginger extracts which showed that garlic (*Allium sativum*) and ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) had high composition of carbohydrate and crude protein which signifies their nutritive values.

Table 3 to Table 6 showed promising activity of the aqueous and ethanol extracts of ginger and garlic in comparison with the conventional antibiotics. The inhibitory effect of the extracts was dose dependant.

Table 1: Phytochemical analysis of the garlic and ginger extracts

Parameter	Garlic extract		Ginger extract	
	Aqueous	Ethanol	Aqueous	Ethanol
Alkaloids	+	+	+	+
Saponin	+	+	+	+
Flavonoid	+	+	+	+
Steroid	-	+	-	+
Tannin	+	+	+	+
Cardiac glycoside	+	+	+	+

Key: + = Present - = Absent

Table 2: Proximate composition of garlic (*Allium sativum*) and ginger (*Zingiber officinale*)

Parameters	Garlic	Ginger
Moisture	0.02	0.03
Ash	2.0	3.0
Lipid	2.0	13.0
Crude protein	18.0	14.0
Crude fibre	0.1	0,67
Carbohydrate	77.88	69.3

Table 3: Zone of inhibition of aqueous extract of garlic

Test organisms	50 mg/ml	25 mg/ml	12.5 mg/ml	6.25 mg/ml	Ciprofloxacin	SDW
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	20.11±0.01	15.00±1.00	13.20±0.01	10.10±0.01	14.10±0.01	NA
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	22.01±0.20	20.00±0.01	17.00±0.20	15.00±0.02	15.01±0.03	NA
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	25.10±0.02	23.10±0.03	20.03±0.01	15.00±0.01	16.20±1.00	NA
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	25.02±0.20	20.12±0.20	17.11±0.01	15.00±1.00	15.10±0.01	NA
<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	23.00±0.03	19.01±0.02	14.03±0.01	12.00±0.10	14.11±0.01	NA

Key: Mean ± SEM, SDW – Sterile distilled water (Negative control), Ciprofloxacin (Positive control), NA – No activity

Table 4: Zone of inhibition of ethanol extract of garlic

Test organisms	50 mg/ml	25 mg/ml	12.5 mg/ml	6.25 mg/ml	Ciprofloxacin	SDW
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	28.11±0.01	25.00±1.00	20.20±0.01	16.11±0.01	14.10±0.01	NA
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	24.01±0.20	19.00±0.01	16.00±0.20	13.00±0.02	15.01±0.03	NA
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	25.01±0.02	22.10±0.03	17.03±0.01	13.10±0.01	16.20±1.00	NA
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	25.02±0.20	20.12±0.20	16.01±0.01	12.00±1.00	15.10±0.01	NA
<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	23.00±0.01	18.01±0.01	14.01±0.01	11.00±0.10	14.11±0.01	NA

Key: Mean ± SEM, SDW – Sterile distilled water (Negative control), Ciprofloxacin (Positive control), NA – No activity

Table 5: Zone of inhibition (mm) of aqueous extract of ginger

Test organisms	50 mg/ml	25 mg/ml	12.5 mg/ml	6.25 mg/ml	Ciprofloxacin	SDW
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	13.01±0.01	11.10±1.00	7.20±0.01	5.00±0.01	14.10±0.01	NA
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	18.01±0.20	15.00±0.01	10.00±0.20	7.00±0.02	15.01±0.03	NA
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	16.01±0.02	13.00±0.03	10.03±0.01	7.03±0.03	16.20±1.00	NA
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	17.02±0.20	13.12±0.20	11.11±0.01	9.00±1.00	15.10±0.01	NA
<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	17.00±0.03	14.01±0.02	11.03±0.01	12.01±0.10	14.11±0.01	NA

Key: Mean ± SEM, SDW – Sterile distilled water (Negative control), Ciprofloxacin (Positive control), NA – No activity

Table 6: Zone of inhibition (mm) of ethanol extract of ginger

Test organisms	50 mg/ml	25 mg/ml	12.5 mg/ml	6.25 mg/ml	Ciprofloxacin	SDW
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	20.11±0.01	16.00±1.00	12.20±0.01	9.00±0.01	14.10±0.01	NA
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	24.01±0.20	20.00±0.01	16.00±0.20	10.00±0.02	15.01±0.03	NA
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	19.11±0.02	15.00±0.03	10.03±0.01	5.03±0.03	16.20±1.00	NA
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	22.02±0.20	17.12±0.20	13.11±0.01	9.00±1.00	15.10±0.01	NA
<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	16.00±0.03	12.01±0.02	9.03±0.01	5.01±0.10	14.11±0.01	NA

Key: Mean ± SEM, SDW – Sterile distilled water (Negative control), Ciprofloxacin (Positive control), NA – No activity

Table 7: Minimum inhibitory concentration of aqueous extract of garlic

Test organisms	50 mg/ml	25 mg/ml	12.5 mg/ml	6.25 mg/ml	MIC (mg/ml)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	-	-	+	+	25
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	-	+	+	+	50
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	+	+	+	+	Nil
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	-	+	+	+	50
<i>Streptococcus</i>	-	+	+	+	50

*pneumoniae***Table 8: Minimum inhibitory concentration of ethanol extract of garlic**

Test organisms	50 mg/ml	25 mg/ml	12.5 mg/ml	6.25 mg/ml	MIC (mg/ml)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	-	-	-	+	12.5
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	-	-	+	+	25
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	-	-	+	+	50
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	-	+	-	+	12.5
<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	-	+	-	+	12.5

Table 9: Minimum inhibitory concentration of aqueous extract of ginger

Test organisms	50 mg/ml	25 mg/ml	12.5 mg/ml	6.25 mg/ml	MBC (mg/ml)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	-	+	+	+	50
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	-	-	+	+	25
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	-	+	+	+	50
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	-	-	+	+	25
<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	-	+	+	+	50

Table 10: Minimum inhibitory concentration of ethanol extract of ginger

Test organisms	50 mg/ml	25 mg/ml	12.5 mg/ml	6.25 mg/ml	MBC (mg/ml)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	-	-	+	+	25
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	-	-	+	+	25
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	-	-	+	+	25
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	-	+	+	+	50
<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	-	-	+	+	25

DISCUSSION

Medicinal plants play a significant role in providing primary health care services to rural communities. The results in Table 1 revealed the presence of phytochemicals such as alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, steroids, tannin, steroid and cardiac glycoside. This result is in agreement with the research of Oshomoh *et al.* (2016) where similar phytochemicals compounds were revealed in an analysis carried out on ginger and garlic extracts. Table 2 results showed that the proximate analysis revealed that garlic and ginger can be said to be very rich in carbohydrate where garlic had (77.88 %) and ginger (69.30 %). The crude fat content for both extracts were low, the oil can be extracted for use as essential oil (Okwu and Nnamdi, 2008). The crude protein content was high and this could be due to active proteinous metabolites such as allicin, ajoene and capsaicin. These spices are used as supplement since they are mixed with other food in our diet (Dashak *et al.*, 2001). The antibacterial activity of extracts of *Allium sativum* (garlic) and *Zingiber officinale* (ginger) was evaluated against five different bacteria namely *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Streptococcus pneumonia* in this study. The bacterial isolates evaluated in this research are similar to the same bacterial isolates reported by Oshomoh *et al.* (2016). The research of Lawrence *et al.* (2014) reported the use of similar isolates used in this study on ginger and garlic extracts. The results of the antibacterial investigations using the well diffusion method are given in Tables 3-6. The zone of inhibition of the garlic extract was higher than that of the ginger extract for the corresponding concentrations. The diameter for zone of inhibition for aqueous extract of garlic ranged from 10.10±0.01 mm to 25.10±0.03 mm at various concentrations used. The diameter for zone of inhibition for ethanol extract of garlic ranged from 11.00±0.01 mm to 28.11±0.01 mm at various concentrations used. The diameter of zone of inhibition for aqueous extract of ginger ranged from (5.00±0.01 to 18.01±0.03) mm at various concentrations used. The diameter of zone of inhibition for ethanolic extract of ginger ranged from (5.03±0.01 to 24.01±0.20) mm at various concentrations used. Maximum inhibitory effect for aqueous extract of ginger was towards *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, while that of ethanolic was towards *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The results in

Table 3 to Table 6 revealed the efficacy of the extracts used on the bacterial isolates. The extracts were concentration dependent in comparison with the positive control, ciprofloxacin. The result in Table 7 to Table 10 of the MIC and MBC activity of the extracts showed that the activity of the antibacterial activity of both extract is dose dependent. The results for the antibacterial screening have shown that the entire extracts except the water extracts have antibacterial activity. The results of the inhibition of bacterial growth have shown that the extracts are active at high concentration and inactive at very low concentrations. The results in this study are in agreement with the research carried out by Oshomoh *et al.* (2016); Lawrence *et al.* (2014). The research of Mukhtar and Ghori (2012); Akintobi *et al.* (2013) reported the potency of garlic and ginger extracts on wide spectrum of antibacterial activity against Gram negative and Gram positive bacteria such as *Escherichia*, *Salmonella*, *Staphylococcus*, *Streptococcus*, *Klebsiella*, *Proteus*, *Bacillus* and *Clostridium* as also reported in this present study. Thus the study may suggest that the inhibition of bacterial growth activity of the extracts is dose dependent. Allicin has been found to be the active ingredient in garlic and it works as an antimicrobial agent by inhibiting DNA and protein synthesis moderately and inhibiting RNA synthesis completely as a primary target (Shobana *et al.*, 2009; Rahman *et al.*, 2011). Garlic is also rich in anionic components such as nitrates, chlorides and sulfates and other water soluble components found in plants and these components may have antimicrobial properties (Shobana *et al.*, 2009). Previous authors have described the antibacterial activity of garlic extract against microorganisms. Bulbs belonging to the *Allium* genus had the most antibacterial activity against *Streptococcus mutans* (Ohara *et al.*, 2008) and against *Streptococcus agalactiae*. In addition, garlic was shown to have antimicrobial activity against *Streptococcus olaris*, *Streptococcus mitis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* (Silva and Fernandes, 2010; Daka, 2011); *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Shigella flexineri*, *Proteus mirabilis* (Shobana *et al.*, 2009); and *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Few studies have shown some bacteria to be resistant towards garlic extract and these include *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* (Vuddhakul *et al.*, 2007). In ginger, the gingerol related components have been found to have antimicrobial activities

(Rahman *et al.*, 2011). There are several reports of the inhibitory effect of ginger in the form of extract against several bacteria (Joe *et al.*, 2009; Patel *et al.*, 2011). Moderate to good antimicrobial properties of ginger were shown in previous studies (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2003; Singh *et al.*, 2008; Venugopal *et al.*, 2009). However, some studies have reported as ginger having weak antimicrobial effects (Indu *et al.*, 2006; Eruteya and Odunfa, 2009; Esimone *et al.*, 2010; Silva and Frenandes, 2010) and it compares well with this study where ginger had reduced antimicrobial activity. The results of this present study has shown that test organisms were susceptible to crude extracts of garlic and ginger *in vitro* which means the plant has antibacterial property. It is hereby recommended that further research be done towards isolating, purifying and standardizing the active antibacterial ingredients in both plant materials.

CONCLUSION

The present study has provided some comparative studies on the phytochemical, antimicrobial and proximate content of garlic and ginger. This is a clear indication that these two spices which are commonly used among humans are nutritional and of great health benefits.

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